

CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE CHALLENGE OF GLOBAL SECURITY & SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: THE SCHISM BETWEEN THE UNITED STATES AND CHINA IN FOCUS

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ABSTRACT

The planet has undergone repeated distortion through human-related activities. The renewed activities of science and technological advancements of an industrialized craze world has left our environment under regular pollution and all forms of degradation. The resultant climate change has been major threats to life (man, animal and plants) and our environment. This phenomenon has attracted global attention since the 1980s. Thus, this paper is an addition to the discourse on climate change. This paper adopts the secondary source of data collection. Works of several scholars on climate change were presented and analyzed. The main polluters of global environment; the us and china were also spotlighted. The paper concludes by calling for more commitment of the industrialized world to adhere to the climate change protocols to ensure that the target of 1.5°C global temperature by 2050 is achievable and rid the world of the negative consequences of global warming. Some recommendations including a prompt migration by industrialized states from fossil fuels usage to renewable energy were made. This paper is of tremendous value to scholars who are interested in finding solution to the challenge of global warming and it's adverse consequences.

Keywords: *Fossil Fuel, Sustainable Development Goals(Sdgs), Cop26, Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Global Security And Climate Change.*

INTRODUCTION

Mankind has been engrossed with several challenges in its effort to make a living and overcome the vagaries posed by his environment. On several occasions, these challenges become so overwhelming that they constitute all life albatross.

Climate change refers to a long term warming of the planet thus causing an increase in global temperature, usually caused by human activities through the release of greenhouse gases such as;

- deforestation and land use changes through degradation.
- burning fossil fuels (such as coal, gas and oil and its by products); and
- impacts of agriculture and livestock production on the environment (Maathai, 2003).

Climate change received significant global attention between the late 1980s and 1990s, with several key events and milestones, contributing to its growing recognition as a pressing international challenge. Some key dates in global attention and a consequent response to climate change started when James Hansen testified as to its damaging effects before the US Senate, stating that climate change has begun and was becoming a global challenge. This is followed by the establishment of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) by the United Nations in 1990 whose report provided a comprehensive assessment of climate change science and impacts (Bond, 2012). The United Nations (UN) continue to drive the process of giving the climate change the global attention it deserves. In 1972, the UN convened a conference on environment and development (Rio Earth Summit) leading to the establishment of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

In 1997, the UN convened Kyoto Protocol produced an International Agreement to reduce greenhouse gas emissions was adopted, marking a significant step towards global cooperation on climate change (Basse, 2012). The Paris Agreement of 2015 under The 15th Conference of Parties (COP 15), signed by almost 200 countries set a global goal to limit warming to well below 2°C and pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C.

The UN, under its International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), keeps promoting the adoption of renewable energy. In the same manner, several summits to address global climate change action plans have been in the works of the UN (Okereke, 2017). The Paris Agreement, climate change of 2015 has remained a central global issue with continued international negotiations, increased public awareness and the growing calls for global actions to contain its impact. Again, in 2015, the United Nations set up a Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of 17 goals and gave 2030 as the target date to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure peace and prosperity for all (Sofriate, 2018).

Finally, the United Nations packaged climate summit held in Glasgow 2021 under COP26 has one of its main agreements to achieve carbon-cutting targets by end of 2022, and dozens of member states have promised to phase out petrol and diesel-powered cars by 2025. But the two biggest pollutants, the US and China displayed much trepidation on compliance to most of the terms of the

glasgow agreement (Maathai, 2003). It is remarkable that the social phenomenon of climate change, which associates all human efforts in the attempt to conquer his environment and become industrialized is becoming counterproductive. As mankind determine to advance in science and technology, the planet and our environment have always been at the receiving end (Monbiot, 2016).

OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

The overall objective of the paper is to interrogate different segments of climate change to deliver a world of a mitigated climate change. To achieve this course the followings are set as pathways:

- 1 To show how climate change contributes to global catastrophe.
- 2 To identify the main contributors to climate change.
- 3 To identify the issues leading to the schism between the united states and china on the climate change mitigation episode.
- 4 To show the challenges climate change poses to global security and sustainable development
- 5 To show global initiatives to address climate change; and
- 6 To recommended some solutions to climate change outcome.

RESEARCJH QUESTIONS

In other to make above stated objectives convenient for proper interrogation, the following research questions were generated:

- 1 How does climate change lead to global catastrophe?
- 2 Who are the main contributors to climate change?
- 3 What led to the schism between the united states and china on the climate change mitigation episode?
- 4 What are the main challenges challenges climate change pose to global security and sustainable development?
- 5 What are the global initiatives to address climate change challenges?
- 6 How do we overcome the ravaging challenges of climate change?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change as an ongoing global challenge has attracted centrality of discourse by various environmental and development scholars around the globe. The works of some notable scholars to be reviewed are given thematic discussion in this session.

Kolbert (2020) dwelt on the far reaching impacts of climate change. To him, the impacts of climate change is overwhelming in various aspects of our life and the environment. Some of the significant impacts are summarized as follows;

A, Rising sea level leading to coastal flooding, sea erosion and salt water intrusion into fresh water. This negative impact has severely devastated our riverine communities in Nigeria. Most of our communities in Escravos River and other coastline grapple with this challenge year in year out.

B, The prevalence of extreme hot weather that increased frequency and intensity of heat wave, drought, storms and wildfire, are now common occurrences in various parts of the globe.

C, The Prevalence Of Scarcity Of Portable Water, caused by changes In Precipitation Pattern, Which Cause Droughts And Water Shortages.

D, Loss of biodiversity; caused by rising temperature, ocean acidification and habitat disruption and threatens the ecosystem.

Today, in most parts of Africa, the heat wave is excessively high, rising beyond 25°C in most cases. This is beyond a threshold of 1.5°C the Glasgow summit of 2021 recommended. The high heat level, occasioned by climate change, is inimical to convenient human life.

E, Food Insecurity is of a great challenge. Climate change impact on agriculture, marine life and livestock lead to crop failures, reduced yields and change of growing season of certain crops (kolbert,2020).

Dwelling more on adverse effects of climate change, wallace-wells (2019) identified the following as focal points;

A, Economic consequences wrought by climate change severely damage infrastructure, increased costs of health care emergency responses and loss of productivity.

B, Warmer temperature is injurious to human life. It increased the spread of diseases, heat stress and other health issues.

C, Climate change leads to social and cultural impacts. Problems of displacement, migration and loss of cultural heritage are occasioned by rising sea levels, extreme weather and devastating environments.

D, Increased ocean acidification that present in decreased ph levels harm marine life - especially coral reefs, shellfish and other calcium carbonate - based organisms.

E, Climate change leads to irreversible changes to critical ecosystems such as melting artic ice, coral bleaching or amazon rainforest die-offs.

Understanding these impacts is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate and adapt to climate change.

Advocating for a zero -sum approach to the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, Frankhauser, S. & Mbow, c. (eds) (2017) defined greenhouse as a structure made of transparent materials such as glass or plastic, in which plants are grown. The term greenhouse can also refer to the natural process by which certain gases in the atmosphere, e.g. carbon dioxide, methane, trap heat, keeping the planet warm. They then gave a rundown of greenhouse gases to include;

- Carbon Dioxide (CO₂)
- Methane (CH₄)
- Nitrous Oxide (N₂O)
- Fluorinated Gases (F-gases)
- Ozone (O₃)
- Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs).

Further, the continuous release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, primarily through human activities like burning fossil fuels, deforestation and agriculture have been recorded to have adverse effects on the environment and should be stopped (Frankhauser, S. & Mbow, C; 2017)

On the impact of Climate Change in global security, (Klein, 2014) refers the phenomenon to the measure and strategy implemented to ensure the safety and protection world's population, environment and interests from threats. These threats include:

1 TRADITIONAL SECURITY THREATS.

- Interstate Conflicts and Wars.
- Nuclear Proliferation
- Terrorism.

2 NON-TRADITIONAL SECURITY THREATS.

- Cyber Security Threats
- Climate Change and Environmental Degradation
- Pandemic and Global Health Crisis
- Migration and Refugee Crisis.

3 EMERGING SECURITY THREATS.

- Artificial Intelligence and Autonomous Weapons.
- Space Security and Satellite Technology
- Biotechnology and Biosecurity.

To Klein, these threats confronting mankind are being compounded by the ravaging climate change adversities (Klein, 2014).

In focusing on the global initiatives to mitigate climate change, (Alim, F. & Dube, O. P.,2018) recounted several global initiatives aimed at addressing the effects of climate change. They include;

1 The Treaty, founded on United Nations Framework Convention On Climate Change (UNFCCC) that aims to stabilize Greenhouse Gas concentrations in the atmosphere.

2 The Paris Agreement on climate change setting a global goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C; and

3 The Enactment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) initiative that sets 17 goals and timelines for achieving global development index. Goal 13, provides for climate control action, a strategy to overcome the negative effects of climate change.

Further on the challenges posed by climate change to global security, (Kolbert, 2020) identified the followings as the most prominent:

- Resource scarcity arising from competition for water, food and energy, which lead to conflicts.
- Mass migration and displacement due to rising sea levels, droughts, harsh weather and environmental pollution. Attendant social and political instability are also of common place.
- the challenge of global governance is also evident in climate change.

As a management of the Green Belt Movement advancing the course of environmental conversations. (Meathai, 2003). To Kolbert (2020), climate change requires international cooperation and collective action, which although can be challenging to achieve. To him, the challenge of social and political instability, particularly among vulnerable states, can be a major outcome of climate change. Most states devastated by harsh environmental conditions have shown signs of restiveness, and became potential source of political agitations and call for regime changes. This has been common occurrences in the Latin America states. Finally, Kolbert (2020) holds that addressing climate change is crucial to mitigating the effects of these global security challenges and ensure a more stable and secured future. (Meathai, 2003)

On strategies for mitigating climate change in Africa through living adaptations, Mbow, C., Fakir, S. and Zhu Z. (2019) called for the development of climate resilient infrastructure and urban planning that will ensure climate conditions compliance.

- They urged citizens to erect residential homes in areas that are not prone to harsh and unfriendly environmental conditions, such as floods and erosion.
- They urged citizens not only to strive towards ecosystem restoration, but to embark on sustainable agriculture and water management efforts to preserve both the environment and ensure water availability.
- they urged citizens to support researches aimed at mitigating negative impact of climate change.
- they urged citizens to use public transportation, cycling or walking to their destinations.
- they urged citizens to cultivate and eat plant-based diet and avoid food wastage.
- they urged citizens to support renewable energy projects and promote climate friendly policies.
- finally, to educate ourselves and others about climate change (Mbow, C., Fakir, S., and Zhu, Z., 2019).

On the schism and complex energy relationship between the United States and China, Wallace-Wells (2019) identified both states as not only global superpowers, but the two highest polluters of global atmosphere. On Greenhouse Gas emissions in the past and present, he identified China as the current world's biggest emitter of carbon dioxide, producing 12.7 billion metric tons of emissions annually. This figure dwarfs that of the United States (US) emissions currently he puts at 5.9 billion metric tons annually. He further holds that since 1850, China has emitted 284 billion tons of carbon dioxide. But the us, which industrialized far earlier, has emitted almost 509 billion, almost twice of china figure. Cumulatively therefore, the US emitted more carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. To him, there has been much schism between the major emitters in the climate change negotiations. Ordinarily, the country with higher historic emissions have a higher burden of contributing more to promote climate change mitigation, but this claim is being

repudiated by the us. Instead, it's insistence has been on the one emitting more at the moment that ought to contribute more to the climate change mitigation efforts. (Wallace-Wells, 2019)

On the knotty issue of emission cuts, Mondiot (2016) opined that both the US and China have not demonstrated enough cooperation. Under President Obama's Administration, the US agreed to cut emissions by at least 26% below 2005 level by the year 2025. While under the Biden administration, us has promised to stop new emissions by 2050. China under Xi Jinping on the other hand, promised in the Paris Agreement to first reach it's peak emissions by 2030 and pledged to increase the share of her non-fossil fuel energy like wind, solar and nuclear to 25%. China promised to become carbon neutral by 2060. On the fossil fuels - gas, oil and coal; Wallace-Wells recorded that the US consumes 20% of the world's oil, while china consumes about 14%. The us is also a top oil exporter. China, on the other hand imports most of it's oil.

The shift from coal to natural gas, a cheaper resource, has helped to lower greenhouse gas emissions. Natural gas now accounts for about 30% of energy use in the US. For China, most of her natural gas, accounting for 9% of it's energy mix, is imported. There has been a 40% decline in coal-fired power generation in the US over the last decade. China on the other hand, burns more coal than the rest of the world combined (US Energy Information Association, 2023). If both major polluters agree to speed up plans to cut greenhouse gas emissions, running same time lines, it would be consequential for the world's efforts to stay within safe limits of global warming.

Further contributing to the schism between the United States and China, Okereke (2023) identified china as the highest manufacturer of solar panels, wind turbines and electric vehicle batteries than any other nation. In 2022, china invested \$546 billion into clean energy; while the United States invested \$141 billion on the same project. (Okereke, 2023). To him, China's Renewable Energy capacity surpassed 1,000 Gigawatts in 2021, four times what it had decade earlier. Wind and Solar now exceeds 300 gigawatts each and predict the country will add up to 150 gigawatts soon. Hydropower, on the other hand, accounts for 16% of China's power generation and nuclear energy provides 5%. One in four cars sold in China in 2023 was an electric vehicle. For the US; wind, solar, hydroelectric power and other forms of renewable power accounts for 21% of the energy mix in 2021. In the us, one in every 17 new cars sold in 2023 was electric. The US under Biden administration has pledged to invest \$370 billion over 10 years into wind, solar, green hydrogen, nuclear energy and other non-fossil fuel power (us energy information association, 2024).

The EU Emission database for global atmospheric research report, 2023 identified the top five emitters of carbon dioxide as follows:

- 1 China emitted 11,535 billion metric tons annually.
- 2 US emitted 5, 107 billion metric tons annually.
- 3 EU emitted 3, 304 billion metric tons annually.
- 4 India emitted 2, 597 billion metric tons annually.

5 Russia emitted 1, 792 billion metric tons annually.

Source: EU Emission database for Global Atmospheric Research Report, 2023.

DATA ANALYSIS

From data generated from the Literature reviewed, the following are responses to the questions formulated from the research objectives:

1 HOW DOES CLIMATE CHANGE LEADS TO GLOBAL CATASTROPHE?

This study has revealed that increase of industrialization is a major reason high emissions of greenhouse gases which is injurious to man, animals and the environment. Climate change contributes to global warming of rising temperature, ocean acidification, disruption of the ecosystem, negative impact on agriculture- marine life and reduced crop yields.

Warmer temperature also leads to rising sea levels, sea erosion, wildfire, water scarcity, human health challenges, degradation of our environment leading to displacement and migration to safer grounds with attendant humanitarian crises associate climate change.

2 WHO ARE THE MAIN CONTRIBUTORS TO CLIMATE CHANGE?

This study has also revealed that the us and china are the two major contributors to global warming through the emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere.

This study shows china's greenhouse gas emissions amount to 12.7 billion metric tons annually, while the United States total emissions is put at 5.9 billion metric tons annually. In cumulative terms, from 1850 till date, the us is shown to surpassed china with 509 billion tons of carbon dioxide emissions, while china's cumulative emissions amount to 284 billion tons.

Other major greenhouse gas emitters are as follows; eu with 3.304 billion metric tons annually, India with 2.597 billion metric tons annually and Russia with 1.792 billion metric tons annually.

3 WHAT LED TO THE SCHISM BETWEEN THE UNITED STATES AND CHINA ON THE CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION EPISODE?

The complex rivalry and disagreement between the two superpowers and major gas emitters over reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and deliver a safer world has remained nagging. At several fora to address climate change mentioned in this paper ends in lack of consensus between the two powers on when to end the greenhouse gas emission. The tension arose over China's insistence that the US with higher cumulative volume of greenhouse gas emission should make more commitment of first in time to shift from gas emissions to usage of renewable energy of clean technology of solar, wind and nuclear than china. Both of them refused to accept a common date to to stop gas emissions. While the United States accepted 2050 as it's new date to end gas flaring, china projects 2060 as the year to become carbon neutral. This schism is not good enough for a world in haste to transit from gas flaring to renewable energy not only to

protect our ecosystem but to greatly limit the huge negative impacts of climate change already mentioned in this paper.

4 WHAT ARE THE MAIN CHALLENGES CLIMATE CHANGE POSE TO GLOBAL SECURITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT?

This paper has shown the great nexus between climate change and global security. A secured world is one that its citizens, marine life and environment are protected from various threats. This paper has identified climate change as a major threat confronting humanity. Greenhouse gas emissions have been identified as the major cause of food insecurity, water scarcity, mass migration and displacement, humanitarian crises, health challenges and global governance challenges.

Global sustainable development efforts have been shown in this paper to be heavily compromised by climate change. It is largely for this reason climate action was made a focal point in the 17 sustainable development goals (sdgs), as goal no. 13. The un under the sdgs initiative projects 2030 as the target date to deliver a world free from gas emissions.

5 WHAT ARE THE GLOBAL INITIATIVES TO ADDRESS CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION?

This paper has been charitable to efforts of the UN and several agencies at every fora created to put the issue of climate change in the front burner of global attention. The creations of various frameworks, conventions, Kyoto protocol of 1997, Paris agreement of 2015, COP26 climate summit in Glasgow from October 31 to November 12, 2021 and the sustainable development goals SDGs initiative of 2015; are all geared to confront the challenge of climate change. It is expected that when the right commitment is shown by all stakeholders, the challenges humanity is facing under climate change if not totally eliminated, will be radically reduced.

6 HOW DO WE OVERCOME THE CHALLENGE OF CLIMATE CHANGE EPISODE RAVAGING THE WORLD?

This paper has shown that little hope remain for the world if efforts are not redoubled by all critical stakeholders to urgently migrate from greenhouse gas emissions to the full implementation of renewable energy projects. The devastating consequences of climate change must be mitigated through the rugged adoption of sourcing renewable energy from wind, solar and hydro electricity, away from greenhouse gas emissions.

CONCLUSION

This paper has presented climate change as the world's greatest enemy. The worst disasters the globe faces are derivable from the adverse effects of climate change. For this reason, the world, particularly the industrialized, need to close ranks, bury their differences and deliver the world from the imminent catastrophe that keeps knocking on our doors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper provides the following as some of its key recommendations;

1 The world should as a matter of urgency, implement various climate change mitigation agreements and protocols to put an end to greenhouse gas emissions. It is a major destroyer of our ecosystem, the promoter of food crises, health hazard and wrought devastation to our environment.

2 We recommend the intensification of the adoption of renewable energy sources that will be environment and health friendly.

3 The UN should be more Thereby ensuring compliance to climate change protocols quicken the pace of renewable sources of energy in the area of compliance, assistance with funds to states that demonstrate the commitment to abolishing gas flares and in the sponsorship of more researches in that regard.

4 Climate Change should be made a compulsory course in every tertiary institution to make the students aware of the vagaries inherent in climate change and to be imbued with the need to develop technology to fast track the migration from gas flaring as a source of energy to renewable sources.

5 world citizens should be educated on how to be conscious of the hazard of climate change, and device ways to live right. Citizens should be advised not to live in erosion prone areas, be proactive and always in the consciousness of environmentally friendly standards. Finally, all citizens should refrain from carrying out actions that will compromise the environment.

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